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Executive Summary

In ACCEPT, as with any R&D project, successful exploitation of solutions and business models is reliant on gathering stakeholder feedback during on products and services from the development stage through to the project's conclusion. To achieve this, a living lab (LL) framework which encourages collaboration between consortium partners and external stakeholders is proposed. This framework comprises of three main stages, see below.

Following the design of this LL framework, various activities have begun to ensure the stakeholder feedback on the solutions offered in ACCEPT is gathered efficiently and effectively.

A project timeline has been defined which provides a blueprint which maps out the three high-level phases of the feedback process. In ACCEPT, these three stages include:

- Pre-validation
- Pilot site living labs
- Large scale demonstration

To ensure a collaborative approach from consortium members, and ensure that the required stakeholder engagements are identified, a hybrid collaboration approach has been implemented. This approach utilized questionnaires, meetings, and discussions to successfully collect information from the perspective of the project and technical coordinators as well as WP, task, and pilot site leaders. Gathering information from these two perspectives allows for GECO to map out essential information of the stakeholder engagement process. Specifically, when engagements will take place, the purpose of the engagement, and who the relevant stakeholders are, can be determined.

From the information gathered in the hybrid collaboration approach, the foundations are in place to begin planning and executing the engagements. In ACCEPT, the three-stage engagement process has been deployed to effectively carry out the broad range of engagements that will be required. This process utilizes a comprehensive planning phase that involves consultations with project partners to discuss and decide upon the most appropriate engagement tools and methodologies to achieve the task, WP and project goals. Once the engagements have taken place, a thorough monitoring and evaluation process ensures the LL engagement activities are assessed and improved where necessary.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of the task

The primary objective of task 3.1 is to define the roadmap of the Living Lab activities in ACCEPT. This includes undertaking activities with consortium partners to identify the key stakeholders and pilot site community members, both B2B and B2C. The work in task 3.1 will also support the recruitment of relevant stakeholders in pilot site activities. An essential component for this task is to define the Living Lab and engagement frameworks to ensure co-creation throughout the project lifespan. This co-creation approach will rely on iteration and open knowledge sharing with both internal and external stakeholders. The outcome of this approach and the activities in task 3.1 is to validate technology against real market and user needs and understand consumption and consumer behaviour.

1.2. Structure of the deliverable

The chapters in this deliverable will consist of:

- Chapter 2 will outline the high-level Living Lab framework that will be the foundation for the engagement process.
- Chapter 3 will describe the three main project stages (pre-validation, pilot site living labs, and large-scale demonstration) in which the engagement activities take place.
- Chapter 4 will outline the hybrid collaboration approach which maps out the 'when', 'what' and 'who' of the engagements.
- Chapter 5 will describe the engagement process used to plan and execute specific engagements.
- Chapter 6 will highlight how the Living Lab framework has been applied in ACCEPT in WP2.
- Chapter 7 consists of concluded remarks and next steps for task 3.1.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

Due to the co-creation aspect of the Living Lab framework defined in task 3.1, there are interdependencies with most tasks and work packages with ACCEPT. Any task that requires feedback from internal or external stakeholders will be dependent on task 3.1. This will include the validation activities of the technological aspects defined in WP2, 4 and 5, the pre-validation and beta testing in WP6. There will be strong links with the demonstration activities performed in WP7, engaging with pilot site stakeholders is an essential component of the Living Lab process. The impact assessment and preliminary business model analysis will also require input from the framework defined in this task. WP9 activities will be closely linked to T3.1 as communication is an important intertwined element of the engagement process.

2. Living lab framework

To deliver a successful go-to-market solution, research and development projects need to ensure that ideas, concepts, business models and many other factors are shared and evaluated with stakeholders relevant to the project, from the initial design phase through to exploitation. The Living Labs (LL) methodology provides such a framework for the co-creation approach in ACCEPT. The aim of the LL methodology is not only to conceptualize the end-user needs in the core elements of a research and development project, such as concept testing, use case selection, business model design, requirement definitions, etc. but to also involve the end-user in the design process through feedback loops. This ensures that end-user and citizen perspectives are considered in all phases of a solution/business model development as opposed to only at the project completion stage (Ballon et al., 2005). This collaborative process brings the design channels of an innovation project closer to the end-user and real market needs which ultimately maximizes the market uptake potential of the project's solutions.

In ACCEPT, the LL framework that will be applied to ensure stakeholder feedback is incorporated into the development of the various solutions can be broken down into a tri-stage approach (Figure 1).

Figure 1 ACCEPT Living Labs Framework

These three stages should be considered as a layered approach to stakeholder engagement. The **project stages** are the high-level blueprint in which the engagements will take place. The **hybrid collaboration approach** is the process of mapping out when the engagements will take place, defining the purpose of these engagements, and establishing which stakeholders need to be engaged. The **engagement process** is clarifying how the engagements will be carried out, defining the methodologies, tools, materials, and partner roles for executing individual engagement activities. These stages are explained in more detail in the following chapters in this document.

3. Project stages

The project stages defined in ACCEPT as part of the LL framework has been designed based on a combination of a LL model proposed by Liedtke (2015) and the validation process suggested in the ACCEPT project. This high-level timeline comprises of three stages, pre-validation, pilot site LLs and a large-scale demonstration, each of these stages have specific aims and locale (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 ACCEPT Living Lab project stages

3.1. Pre-validation testbeds

A rigorous testing and pre-validation phase of the ACCEPT solution will take place in real buildings with already established lab environments. The following locations will serve as a testbed for the actual demonstration activities. The pre-validation testbeds in ACCEPT are listed below.

Historical consumption data – Spain - Viesgo

Viesgo will provide five years of historical records of smart metering (hourly load curves) covering over 90% of its 800,000 customers. This rich pool of data provides valuable information on typical demand profiles, prone to specific actions of demand response (peaky demand, air conditioning, electric heating, etc.). The geographical location of Viesgo's grid in northern Spain covers a wide range of climates, ranging from temperate Atlantic Sea climate to cold mountain climate and a variety of customer profiles. These data will be used for training and validating the engines powering the *Citizen Apps* of ACCEPT.

nZEB - DIH Testbed Facility – Greece – CERTH

The nZEB - DIH testbed facility is a residential building where occupants can experience actual living scenarios, without permanent tenants. It is equipped with a vast variety of sensors, actuators, smart home devices and intelligent robots. The building is fully equipped with energy-related sensors capable of monitoring the consumption of the entire building. The building can operate as a microgrid by utilising the nearby PV plant (approx. 10KWp) and battery unit (approx. 5KWh).

Hypertech Office & HEL Smart Homes – Greece – Hypertech

Hypertech offices are capable of functioning as a laboratory environment while respecting day-to-day business activities. This environment permits research activities in the domain of IoT, flexibility profiling and demand-side management. It is equipped with cutting-edge technology such as sensory equipment, in-home displays, AMI gateways and many other devices that enable the validation of state-of-the-art prototypes. The office accommodates 20 employees who inhabit an open space of approximately 70m² with 9 working desks and several individual office spaces of approximately 12m² that accommodate 1-3 working desks. The HEL Smart Home consists of 9 residential buildings located in the wider region of Athens covering several building types, from small apartments to detached houses. The occupants have voluntarily given their consent and offered their premises for the validation of the Hypertech intelligence tool suite. All involved houses have been equipped with Hypertech's

multi-protocol IoT Gateway to monitor the in-home energy use, resident behaviour and enable smart home control features. HEL Smart Home will be used to test the ACCEPT solution platform at the building and community levels.

3.2. Pilot site living labs

The next phase is to test the ACCEPT solution with a small number of actual users to enable regular feedback loops that aim to eliminate user acceptance issues during the full pilot demonstrations. The pilot site living labs is a bridging phase between the early design and development of solutions in the validation phase and the full deployment in the large-scale demonstration phase. This phase provides the opportunity for fast iterations and regular modifications/refinements to technology and solutions offered in ACCEPT. The location of the pilot site living labs is identical to the large-scale demonstration sites listed in the following subsection.

3.3. Large scale demonstration

The final phase of the project is the full deployment of the ACCEPT solution in all pilot sites. Within this phase, an evaluation of the impact of the ACCEPT solution will be carried out based on key performance indicators. The pilot evaluation framework will aim at continuously monitoring critical impact aspects that include end-user acceptance and comfort, amongst many other dimensions. The ACCEPT pilot sites are carefully selected to address different technical (energy assets, vectors, etc.) and organizational (energy communities, centrally managed communities, etc.) typologies, enabling the demonstration of different validation scenarios and the extraction of added value conclusions and recommendations for the commercial roll-out of the ACCEPT solution. A forthcoming stakeholder and community mapping will be completed for each of the large-scale demonstration sites, allowing for these initial pilot narratives to be expanded upon to include barriers and drivers in relation to energy solutions. The results of this ongoing community narrative work will be described in D3.5 that will be available at M10 (October 2021).

Pilot site 1: Aspra Spitia Community - Greece - Mytilineos

The settlement, "Aspra Spitia", hosts the workers of the nearby Aluminum factory and currently comprises 1,088 residences which occupy 61.3 hectares and host more than 3,000 people. Besides residential buildings, there are educational buildings, public services and infrastructure and retail shops serving the local community. The majority of residents are plant workers, so human relationships forged in the workspace are carried over to the neighbourhood and vice versa creating a strong sense of community. Workers' families are engaged in numerous social activities, including sports, folk and cultural activities, through a number of clubs that are actively supported by Mytilineos. This creates a complex web of social dynamics that encapsulate families, friends and professional and social relations that together formulate a tightly knit community. The settlement includes numerous hubs of 2-story semi-detached houses, forming smaller neighbourhoods, and a 12-story tower located next to the central square, accommodating 24 2-bedroom or 3-bedroom flats as well as multiapartment buildings, single apartments, houses and shops. 19 studio flats facilitate short stays for the on-duty employees who do not reside permanently in Aspra Spitia. In a small settlement at Aghios Nikolaos, there are 32 villas for the plant senior management and 10 guest houses for visitors as well as a conference centre.

Pilot Site 2: Renewable Energy Cooperative Buildings - Spain - LaSolar

LASOLAR is a renewable electricity cooperative in Murcia, a region in southeast Spain 160 km from Argelia's coast with 300 sunny days p.a. on average. The pilot site is located in a city of 250,000 people, surrounded by several small towns. The residences available for the ACCEPT demonstrations range from 10-storey blocks of flats to detached buildings. Resident heating needs are covered either by natural gas/ diesel-powered individual/ centralised units or by electrical heat pumps that gain increasing popularity due to their cost-effectiveness and capability to combine both cooling and heating functions. Murcia pilot site will provide up to 50 residences to engage in demand-side management framework of ACCEPT project, 10 of which are prosumers. Buildings that fulfil the project requirements will be utilised as a platform for the validation of the ACCEPT solution. Given the latest updates in Spanish regulatory framework and the local renewable production potential, the concepts of self-consumption will be investigated on building and community level.'

Pilot Site 3: Eva Lanxmeer Community - Netherlands - EDBR

The Dutch pilot site is a district that will mainly validate the community aggregator concept. Flexibility service provision from a cooperative aggregator will be investigated to balance the portfolio of the energy provider and for local congestion management for the DSO. The revenues gained will be shared with the prosumers in the district. The Eva Lanxmeer community in Culemborg is an established sustainable urban demonstration site and community when the first houses were constructed in 2000. At the Marsmanweg location, the solar roof comprises of 784 panels of 300 Wp each, the charging station is equipped with 6 EV-charging points and a grid-tied energy storage system. At the HR Holststraat location, a second charging lot is installed with 4 charging sockets. Both locations belong to the cooperative Vrijstad Energie B.A. and are equipped with smart meters, smart charging communication

infrastructure and a local power management system. Local grid congestion has been identified as an important issue for the solution of which flexibility-related services provided at an aggregated community level will be required.

Pilot Site 4: Arena Innovation Community & Fondazione la Sosta - Switzerland - AEM

The AEM pilot site in Switzerland consists of the Arena Innovation Community (AIC), which represents a residential area in the suburbs of Lugano and the Fondazione la Sosta (FLS), an elderly care home within the urban area. The residential district consists of approximately 50 residential buildings, a big engineers office, a legal office and a care home (66 guests and 94 workers). The building stock consists of 3 multi-family buildings with 5 floors and three typical two-storey family houses. The building stock hosts approximately 105 residents and covers a total area of approx. 8,000m². The total annual consumption for residential houses is 90,000 kWh (average electricity consumption of 2,200 kWh per year). Office buildings have a total annual consumption of 193,500 kWh (two large offices each and 1 small). Casa Girasole (Assisted Living Facility) has an annual total consumption of 316,000 kWh. Via Motta distribution network is served by a 400kVA substation which is located in the middle of the neighbourhood. There is also the presence of PV plant with a total installed capacity of 60 kWp on the roof of the local shelter for elderly people. The CHP facility provides 140 kWp capacity. The storage for overproduction will be done by a hot water reservoir of 40m³ to enable higher levels of integration of the PVs and shift demand out of the peak hours. Two heat pumps are installed in this area with a capacity of 4.5 kW each. Within the LL framework, this pilot site will investigate an energy community and focus on the elderly care home and the related DERs.

4. Hybrid collaboration approach

With the high-level blueprint in place, the next phase of the ACCEPT LL framework is to identify the 'whos', 'whats' and 'whens' of the engagement actual engagement activities falling within these LL windows. For these purposes, the hybrid collaboration approach (Figure 3) is utilized within the LL framework to provide a road map of the engagements expected to occur throughout the ACCEPT project. This approach consists of two major components: (1) examining the top-down perspective from the project and technical coordinators and (2), gathering information from the bottom-up perspective from work package (WP), task and pilot site leaders. Combining these perspectives allows for the broad project goals to be aligned with ground-level needs, which is essential for planning the stakeholder engagement activities. In addition to its function for planning the engagements activities, the hybrid approach fosters collaboration between the various work packages and diminishes the risk of partners working in silo. Prior to undergoing activities to determine the top-down and bottom-up perspectives, a LL committee was formed. This committee consists of one company representative from each work package and pilot site leader and the project and technical coordination partners. Representatives from this committee take part in monthly meetings held by the leaders of task 3.1.

Figure 3 Living Lab Hybrid Collaboration Approach

4.1. Top-down

The primary aim of the top-down element of the Hybrid collaboration approach is to determine the key stages at which stakeholder feedback will be required. To this end, project and technical coordinators were requested to provide a high-level timeline that outlines when stakeholder feedback is needed, the purpose of the feedback, which ACCEPT WPs need to be involved in, and whether the engagement activity will gather feedback from internal or external stakeholders. The project coordinators have a broad overall view of the project, whilst the technical coordinators are responsible for the technologies being developed that are fundamental to the ACCEPT solution. Therefore, the coordination team is best positioned to provide an overview of expected engagements throughout the project lifespan.

To gather information to produce the high-level timeline, an ACCEPT project timeline template (Appendix A) was completed by the coordinators of the ACCEPT project. Table 1 displays the information gathered from this template. In total, 14 engagements were identified, four with internal stakeholders, four with external stakeholders and six with internal and external. These engagements span through WP2 – WP8 and take place from month 3 to project completion at month 42.

It is essential to determine the timeline of when and what feedback will be required, however, it is equally important to maintain the ethos that the feedback required throughout the project needs to have an element of flexibility. Thus, timeframes and aims proposed in this roadmap should be adjusted according to project progression, identification of new goals and results from previously gathered feedback.

Table 1 Top-down inputs: ACCEPT project engagement timeline

Date	Stakeholder	Feedback required	WP(s) involved
M3-4	Internal	Selection of moderators for each pilot site country by GECO	WP3
M5	External	1 st site visits to pilot locations – Identification and engagement with relevant stakeholders; interviews; identification of drivers and barriers for DR services	WP3 (T3.4)
M6	External and internal	Collection of market actors' and prosumers' requirements	WP2 (T2.1)
M10	Internal	Feedback per pilot site on Business Cases-Use Cases-System Architecture and Measurement & Verification Methodology	WP2 (T2.2-2.3)
M10-13	External and Internal	Participation in ex-ante pilot surveys	WP6 (T6.1)
M12-15	External and internal	Feedback on Service Level Agreements and contract terms for the business models and services	WP2 (T2.5)
M15-16	External and internal	Feedback on ACCEPT system 1 st prototype	WP7 (T7.1), WP6 (T6.2), WP4, WP5
M18-M21	Internal	Feedback of pre-validation results	WP6 (T6.4)
M20-24	External	Scheduling of installation activities and training of pilot participants	WP6 (T6.5, T6.6)
M26-27	External and internal	Feedback on ACCEPT system 2 nd prototype	WP7 (T7.1), WP6 (T6.2), WP4, WP5, WP7, WP8
M27-M33	External and Internal	Feedback on obstacles for DR application in energy communities	WP8 (T8.1)
M35-36	External and internal	Feedback on ACCEPT system final version	WP7 (T7.1), WP6 (T6.2), WP7, WP8
M37-40	External	Feedback on business models	WP8 (T8.4)

M37-M42	External	Feedback on exploitable results & business potential	WP8 (T8.2)
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4.2. Bottom-up

The aim of the bottom-up aspect of the hybrid approach is to ensure the perspectives and needs of task and work package leaders, as well as demo site representatives, are considered. A task ID questionnaire (Appendix B) was administered to work package leaders who, with the help of task leaders, identified potential engagements that may be required within their WPs. The primary details they are required to provide in the task ID questionnaire include the partner responsible for the task, when the engagements will occur, the purpose of the engagement, the target stakeholder categories, and the methodology of the engagement. In addition to gathering important information, the task ID questionnaire encourages work package and task leaders to consider the engagements related to their tasks and allows them to provide their perspective on what engagement is expected or required. Table 2 provides a summary of the information provided by WP and task leaders in ACCEPT (this is an ongoing process and some information from WP leaders is yet to be received).

Table 2 Bottom-up inputs: Engagement scoping

Date	Target Audience	Purpose of engagement	WP(s) involved	Task	Partner
M3-M4	Research & Academia Related EU projects Public authorities ESCO TSO Technology experts EU organisations Pilot partners	To gain expert feedback on end-user requirements	WP2	T2.1	RINA-C
M6	Retailer Aggregator ESCO	To extract requirements for the necessary sensors	WP4	T4.1 (1st iteration)	Hypertech
M6	Building manager Facility manager	To extract requirements for the SRI component	WP4	T4.2 (1st iteration)	Hypertech
M6	Retailer Aggregator ESCO	To extract requirements on the business cases from the relevant stakeholders	WP4	T4.5 (1st iteration)	Hypertech
M7	Related EU project	Gain experience and knowledge about possible 'bottlenecks'	WP6	T6.1	CERTH
M15	Building manager Facility manager	To get feedback for the IoT from the end-user	WP4	T4.1 (2nd iteration)	Hypertech
M15	Building manager Facility manager	To get feedback on the module from the end-users	WP4	T4.2 (2nd iteration)	Hypertech

M15	Retailer Aggregator ESCO	To get feedback on the module from the end-users	WP4	T4.5 (2nd iteration)	Hypertech
M20	Citizen/building resident	Talk about possible issues with the citizens that will be directly involved in the demonstration activities	WP6	T6.5	CERTH
M24	Building manager	To collect necessary data for the instantiation of each individual household	WP4	T4.3	Hypertech
M24	Facility manager Citizen/building resident	To get feedback on the module from the end-users. To collect necessary data for the instantiation of each individual household	WP4	T4.4	Hypertech
TBD	Retailer Aggregator ESCO Citizen/Building resident Building manager Facility manager Prosumer/Consumer	TBD	WP2	T2.3	RINA-C
M1-M42	All consortium partners	Stakeholder and citizen engagement through dissemination and communication activities	WP9	T9.1 – T9.5	EEE

To collect the perspectives of the demonstration site leaders, a similar questionnaire has recently been sent to the demo leaders (Appendix C), information from these questionnaires will be presented in later versions of the deliverable. The demo site questionnaire serves the same purpose as the task ID questionnaire in that it gathers information on the required engagements and relevant stakeholders. The exception is that this document is tailored to gather information within a local context and aims to understand the needs relevant to the pilot area. This, in combination with the task-level considerations, will allow for a comprehensive mapping of the bottom-up considerations for the LLs.

5. Engagement process

The fundamental component of LLs is stakeholder engagement. The previous steps in the LL framework work to define the target audience, timing, and objective of the engagement has been defined. In the final step, the focus shifts towards determining the best methodologies and tools to implement these engagements. In ACCEPT, a standardized process will be used to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate stakeholder engagement activities that will occur across various WPs, tasks, and pilot sites (Figure 4). These three stages will be explained in more detail in the following subsections of this chapter.

Figure 4 Three stage engagement process

5.1. Engagement plan

The goal at this stage is to expand upon the 'what', 'when' and 'who', outlined in the hybrid collaboration approach. To achieve this, discussions will take place between GECO, the relevant WP, task or pilot leader and the necessary project/technical coordinators. These discussions will clarify various details, such as how stakeholders will be recruited, what kind of material/content needs to be created and shared with stakeholders and what output is expected. This clarification stage allows GECO to propose the most appropriate methodology (e.g. quantitative or qualitative data collection, interviews, focus groups, surveys, etc.), mode of interaction (e.g. PPT presentations, interactive workshops), and materials (e.g. forms, online platforms) to gather the required feedback from the engagements.

As the primary goal of these meetings is to transform a potential plan into a concrete activity, discussions between GECO and the relevant partners involved in the engagements should take place approximately 6-8 weeks before the planned date of the engagement. This approximate timeframe ensures discussion does not take place too far in advance, which has the potential risk that interactions are planned based on outdated information, or too late. The topics that will be covered will vary between the various engagements, however, the main issues that will be covered in this pre-engagement discussion meeting are likely to include:

- Clarification on any ambiguous information from the questionnaires, (e.g. missing information).
- Refining what exactly needs to be validated (e.g. business requirements or concept) and formulating specific questions to be answered through the engagement activity.
- Discuss how the WPLs plan to recruit identified stakeholders and determine if all the stakeholder categories outlined in the ID questionnaire completed by WP/task leaders are required.
- Refining stakeholder groups or categories to a specific contact.
- Discuss the most appropriate method of engagement.

- Determining if different engagement strategies are required for the various stakeholders identified as relevant to the task or if tasks goals can be addressed through combined stakeholder group engagements to maximise efficiency.
- Determining how the solution, service, business model, etc., will be presented to the stakeholder to gather their feedback (e.g. Trello, Word/Excel file, PowerPoint Presentation, Infographics).
- Designing the material being presented to the stakeholder and identifying any related issues, such as if different materials are required for internal compared to external stakeholders.
- Identifying the most appropriate channel or format for the engagement interaction (e.g. email exchanges, video conference, etc.).
- Identifying the expected output from the engagements.
- Discussing potential goals of the engagements (which can also be translated into KPIs) for assessing the stakeholder consultation process.
- Determining the most efficient way to document the outcomes from the stakeholder engagements to enable feedback loops.
- Discuss how GECCO and other project partners can help with any issues related to the engagements.

5.2. Engagements

At this stage, all the necessary details will have been defined so the engagement can be executed effectively. Engagements are likely to be carried out by the project coordinator or task/WP/demo lead with the assistance of GECCO. At this stage, it is also crucial to establish the best tools and methodologies to carry out the engagement activities as well as determine the roles and responsibilities of the partners involved.

5.2.1. Tools and Methodologies

There are a wide variety of tools and methodologies that may be used to carry out the engagement work. Table 3 lists examples of the potential tools and methodologies that may be utilized throughout the project. Given the current social distancing and travel restrictions related to COVID-19, this list includes various supporting tools that may help to facilitate conducting these methodologies remotely. It is important to note that this is not an exhaustive list, and additional tools or methodologies may also be considered. As the COVID-19 situation improves, it is the ambition of the ACCEPT consortium to look for opportunities to transition these engagements towards an in-person format whenever possible.

To ensure the implementation method is as effective as possible, it is important that each activity is tailored to the engagement's scope and objectives. That is, rather than simply assigning a fixed number of events (e.g. three workshops per pilot), the approach for the LLs is to go a step further and use a dynamic combination of engagement methodologies and tools based on the specific needs of each pilot community (e.g. LL committee participation, stakeholder interviews, usability focus group, pilot narrative article). Furthermore, selecting the most appropriate methodology will be related to the preference of the task leader and the stakeholder being engaged. Therefore, it is anticipated that each pilot will have its own unique engagement plan that speaks to the individual needs of that location. These pilot-specific engagement roadmaps will be detailed in D3.5.

Table 3 ACCEPT Living Lab engagement tools

Scope	Goal	Methods	Tools
Pilot communication & engagement	Provide contextualised communication content for each pilot community. This includes localised messaging designed to generate interest and acceptance of the ACCEPT solutions and to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot branding • Pilot narratives • Pilot sheets/brochures • Product sheets/brochures • Flyers/Posters • Invitation templates • Share-back newsletters • Webinars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tribe (community platform) • Geo Design (negotiation tool) • Consul (citizen participation tool) • Jamboard (brainstorming tool)

	recruit participants for co-creation activities.		
Co-creation	Engage pilot-participants activities designed to 1) explore the community's needs and concerns related to the topic of energy communities and 2) collect feedback on the ACCEPT solutions themselves (e.g. usability, functionalities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Focus groups • Workshops • Questionnaires • User testing • User experience questionnaire (UEQ) • System usability scale (SUS) • Performance analytics • Citizen juries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maptionnaire (map-based survey software) • Alchemer (survey software) • Balsamiq (wireframing software) • Microsoft Teams • Jamboard (brainstorming tool)
Stakeholder mapping & analysis	Define the pilot goals, identify the target audience, explore subjective perspectives, and understand community dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q methodology • Needs-Opportunities-Abilities analysis • Interest/influence mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UXPressia (customer journey mapping software) • Alchemer (survey software)
Living Lab collaboration	Identify synergies between WP3 and all other ACCEPT tasks to create a comprehensive and cohesive LL plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Living Lab committee • Task ID questionnaire • Demo questionnaire • Project timeline template 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trello (brainstorming tool) • Miro (team collaboration software) • Mural (visual collaboration tool) • Microsoft Teams

5.2.2. Roles and Responsibilities

Another important aspect of the stakeholder engagement activities is determining the roles and responsibilities of all partners involved. Table 4 outlines the roles and responsibilities of the LL leader, project and technical coordinators, demo partners and WP or task leaders.

Table 4 ACCEPT Living Lab roles and responsibilities

LL Leader	
Role	Implement LL methodology and provide guidance for the planning and execution of the engagement activities.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and regularly updating the engagement strategy based on the ongoing evolution of the community • Evaluation of LL and engagement activities • Providing guidance on selecting the target audience • Providing guidance on communication material development • Supporting with workshop facilitation • Assist in building stakeholder community • Running LL forum • Communicate LL engagement needs between project leaders and WP/demo site leaders
Project and Technical Coordinator	
Role	Provide an overview of project goals in relation to stakeholder engagement needs.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide an engagement timeline

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage with external/ non-local stakeholders that are of importance to the overall project activities. Representatives of the project in BRIDGE, BDVA and other initiatives (T9.4) Organize relevant activities and facilitate such activities
Demo partners	
Role	The primary facilitator of the engagement initiatives at pilot sites and at the local level.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being the primary point of contact for stakeholders in the local region. Collaborate with GECO to determine appropriate engagement activities. Organizing meetings and events (emails, invitations, arranging meeting space and materials, etc.) Providing communication content Facilitating workshops (or arranging for a facilitator) Recruiting stakeholders
WP Leaders	
Role	Facilitating engagement initiatives at all stages. Information provider on ACCEPT WPs and tasks in relation to stakeholder engagement
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform LL leader about tasks and targeted stakeholders Being the primary point of contact for stakeholders Collaborate with GECO to determine appropriate engagement activities within WP or tasks. Organizing meetings and events (emails, invitations, arranging meeting space and materials, etc.) Providing communication content Facilitating workshops (or arranging for a facilitator) Recruiting stakeholders

5.3. Evaluate, update and next steps

The final phase of the three-stage engagement process refers to how the information and experience gained from the engagements are fed back into the project. It is also important to evaluate the engagement methodology. A stakeholder consultation register (Appendix D) will be used to record the details of any engagement activity undertaken. This register provides a record of all engagements that have occurred and provides details on who was engaged, the aims, if the aims were achieved and how the feedback gathered is fed back into the project. The activity can also be evaluated on factors such as the methodology and materials used to carry out the engagement. This stage should also be used as a checkpoint to decide on what the results of the engagement mean and the next steps to be taken.

It is important at this stage to ensure the outcomes of the engagements are aligned with the KPIs and milestones of the ACCEPT project. Table 5 lists the KPIs identified for ACCEPT relevant to the stakeholder engagement in LLs.

Table 5 ACCEPT KPIs related to the LL process

Category	KPI	Metric	Target
Co-creation / feedback loops/ UX	Co-creation participation	Stakeholders participating in co-creation process	1000
Customer Satisfaction	Citizen satisfaction	Citizen satisfaction from the ACCEPT solution demonstration	Above 75%
Acceptance	Acceptance	Conscious acceptance of the ACCEPT solution	Above 90%
Engagement	Stakeholder engagement	Engaging citizens in the demonstration activities	700
		Engaging stakeholders in the co-creation process	1000

6. Application of living labs

To demonstrate the tri-layered approach utilized in the LL process, we can examine its application thus far in Task 2.1 of WP2 in ACCEPT (see Figure 5).

Within the **LL framework**, WP2 activities fall under the pre-validation stage.

Inspection of the information gathered from the **hybrid approach** shows that from the top-down perspective, feedback on the requirements from market actors and prosumers is expected by M6. From the bottom-up perspective, the Task ID questionnaire provided by WP2 leaders confirms that as part of T2.1, engagements with various stakeholders (e.g., ESCOs, TSOs, Public authorities, amongst others) is expected to gain feedback on end-user requirements before M6.

With regards to the **engagement methodology**, T2.1 is currently in the engagement planning phase of the engagement methodology. Discussions have begun between WP2 representatives from RINA-C and the LL leaders from GECCO. These discussions have focused on clarifying the methodology and related materials to be utilized to gather the required feedback. The outcome of these discussions has identified that an online survey will be administered to a variety of stakeholders across various countries. In addition, the monthly LL meeting in ACCEPT will be used as a forum to allow the task leader from T2.1 to introduce and explain the survey which will be completed by various internal partners. The engagement planning discussions will continue in order to refine details such as the questionnaire content and identify the specific stakeholders that will be targeted to complete the survey.

Figure 5. Overview of the LL frameworks application in T2.1 of WP2

7. Conclusions

Thus far, task 3.1 has established the Living Lab framework which provides the foundation for collaboration and feedback generation through stakeholder engagement. The process, tools and methodologies required for planning and executing engagements has been identified and a strategy to evaluate and measure the progress of the engagements in the Living Lab framework has been established. This framework has been applied in the first 3 months of the project through the establishment of the LL committee and initial work in the hybrid collaboration approach. Future deliverables will describe engagements that have taken place and evaluate their success through comparisons with the defined KPIs and utilising the tools described here such as the stakeholder consultation register.

8. References

Ballon, P., Pierson, J., & Delaere, S. (2005). Test and experimentation platforms for broadband innovation: Examining European practice. Available at SSRN 1331557.

Liedtke, C., Baedeker, C., Hasselkuß, M., Rohn, H., & Grinewitschus, V. (2015). User-integrated innovation in Sustainable LivingLabs: an experimental infrastructure for researching and developing sustainable product service systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 97, 106-116.

9. Appendices

9.1. Appendix A: Timeline template

We need information that allows us to create a timeline of the engagement activities that are expected to take place throughout the ACCEPT project.

We are aware that plans are most likely not in place that allow you to state exact times and dates of all engagements over the next 3/4 years, but please provide any details you can with approx. times, this way we can generate a planned timeline of engagements from a top-down, high-level perspective that can be mapped onto the perspective of WP/task/demo leaders. This way we can have a full picture and align perspectives which is extremely helpful for engagement planning purposes.

Table 1 is the template we would like you to fill out. Underneath this we have provided an example of what we are looking for (Table 2), as well as a roadmap (Figure 1) that can be produced from the details you provide.

Table 1. Please fill out

Date (state the project month you expect the engagement to take place)	Stakeholder (state whether the stakeholder to be engaged is part of the consortium (internal) or not (external)).	Feedback required (please give a short description of the type of feedback you require from the engagement)	WP(s) involved (please state which WPs in ACCEPT will need to be involved in the engagement)

Table 2. Example of timeline details

Date	Stakeholder	Feedback required	WP(s) involved
M3	Internal & external	Feedback on use cases from Business Users.	WP2
M8	Internal	Feedback on technical requirements.	WP4
M10	Internal	Feedback on preliminary business models.	WP10
M12	Internal	Assessment of barrier to innovation	WP2
M14	External	Feedback on preliminary business models.	WP10
M18	External	Assessment of barrier to innovation	WP2
Etc....			

9.2. Appendix B: Task ID questionnaire

Introduction

Stakeholder engagement and market actor validation of our project activities and findings are important aspects of ACCEPT. Our role as GECO is to facilitate interactions, establish feedback loops with stakeholders and support recruitment for other relevant activities. Therefore, we would like you to answer a few questions about current and planned activities (it might seem early for some of the tasks, but please provide preliminary plans as best you can). Providing this information will allow GECO to gather information and understand the needs and plans at the work package and task level, which can then be aligned with broader project goals. This hybrid methodology means GECO can then co-ordinate engagements throughout the project and across work packages, ensuring you collect the feedback you need for your work in an optimal and timely manner. Furthermore, providing knowledge of the type of information and feedback work package leaders are interested in and who they could get it from, will allow GECO to suggest appropriate engagement activities, as well as guidelines and materials to carry out activities.

Purpose of the document

Help GECO understand which aspects of your work package you would like to involve stakeholders (e.g. to discuss new business models, market appetite, to understand drivers and barriers to offerings, etc.), who the stakeholders are you want to collaborate with and obtain feedback from, when these engagement activities need to take place, and what you hope to gain from engagements.

Before proceeding to the Stakeholder Consultation Plan table on the last page, please read the following section on stakeholder categorisation below to assist you in filling out the plan, guide your thoughts and follow a consistent approach across work packages and task.

Stakeholders

Project affiliation

- Internal (project partner)
- External (non-project partner)

Scope

- Pilot area stakeholders (contextualising the stakeholder exchanges to your local circumstances and needs are important)
- Pilot national stakeholders
- EU level stakeholders (e.g. ACER, eu.ESCO)
- 3rd EU country stakeholders

Categories

Energy Sector

- Retailers
- Aggregator
- DSO
- TSO
- ESCO
- Technology provider
- Regulator

End users

- Citizen/Building resident
- Building manager
- Facility managers
- Business managers
- Prosumers/Consumers

Facilitators

- Research/Academic institute
- EU Institutions (EC, EU science foundation)
- National public authorities (industrial committees, municipalities)
- Related EU projects
- Organisations & EU alliances in topics addressed by ACCEPT
- EU technology platforms and respective clusters
- Public bodies and environmental organisations

Stakeholder consultation plan

Please fill out the Stakeholder Consultation Plan table below and include as much detail and information as possible. The more concrete your answers are, the more concrete we can be with the suggestions given with regards to an engagement plan.

Therefore, if you intend to undertake engagements in the next few months, please take the time to come up with a clear picture of who you want to engage and the goal of this engagement.

If you do not have concrete plans at the moment, then please provide any provisional plans that you have. Please also coordinate with the task leaders if you think it necessary.

Remember that planning stakeholder engagements is an iterative process, so the information provided here will be followed up on any further correspondence or discussion will be arranged as appropriate

When completing the stakeholder consultation plan, please:

- Consider all the stakeholder categories listed in the previous tab
- Be as precise as possible as to the purpose of the stakeholder engagement (what do you expect as an outcome e.g., expert opinion, statistics, data)

<p><i>Create as many rows as necessary</i></p>	<p><i>Please link the stakeholder engagement activity to a specific Work Package / Task / Deliverable</i></p>	<p><i>Please describe as precisely as possible the purpose of the stakeholder engagement (what outcome do you expect? e.g. expert opinion, statistics, data)</i></p>	<p><i>Please list the different stakeholders you wish to engage.</i></p>					<p><i>Describe how will the feedback gained from the engagement be utilised in ACCEPT</i></p>	<p><i>Does the engagement work relate to other work packages and/or will the output of the engagement be used in other parts of the project (other tasks and work packages)? Our goal is to avoid unnecessary engagements by combining them across tasks or WPs if and when possible</i></p>	<p><i>Project month the engagement is supposed to happen</i></p>
Engagement #	Relevant Work Package / Task / Deliverable	Purpose of the engagement	Internal or External	Stakeholder category	Stakeholder Scope	Organisation Name (if known)	Organisation country	Impact to the project	Other WPs	Timeline

1 (Example)	WP4 / Task 4.4 / D4.4	To gain expert feedback on desirability of business models	External	DSO	Pilot national stakeholder	Energy X	Finland	Identify if the proposed business models are of value which can then inform the design of these models	WP10	M14
2										
3										
4										
5										
6										

9.3. Appendix C: Demo site questionnaire

Demo Site Questionnaire

Demo Partner:

The goals of this questionnaire are to help us understand:

- What you, the demo partner/leader, wants to achieve in this project
- Which stakeholders we need to involve in the co-creation process to improve the ACCEPT services and products being developed at your demo site

A few things to keep in mind:

- Think of this as a brainstorming exercise to get the conversation started. We know it's very early in the project and that is very likely that this information may change over time. Your answers today will offer us a useful starting point so we can start working in the right direction.
- Your answers don't have to be long (bullet points are welcome).
- If your answers differ per use case, please specify which use case you are referring to in your responses in ALL questions or you can send back multiple questionnaires if you feel it is clearer.

Stakeholders

A major part of the co-creation process in the living labs process are the stakeholders needed for providing input and feedback. Therefore, the table below is a high-level categorisation of potential stakeholders to guide your thoughts. When answering the following questions, please try to think of all the categories below and be as precise as possible as the purpose of the stakeholder engagement will be multi-fold. For instance, it will not be enough to say "Customers" as stakeholders, but try to explain who is the customer, is it a household, an office building, a solar plant, a power plant, a DSO? Also keep in mind that this is not an exhaustive list, so please don't be restricted only to these stakeholder categories.

Stakeholders	
Project affiliation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Internal• External
Categories	Energy Sector <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Retailers• Aggregator• DSO

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TSO • ESCO • Technology provider • Regulator <p>End users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen/Building resident • Building manager • Facility managers • Business managers • Prosumers/Consumers <p>Facilitators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research/Academic institute • EU Institutions (EC, EU science foundation) • National public authorities (industrial committees, municipalities) • Related EU projects • Organisations & EU alliances in topics addressed by ACCEPT • EU technology platforms and respective clusters • Public bodies and environmental organisations
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Questions

1. What are your primary goals for your demo site? What do you want to achieve? What would you consider a successful outcome?

2. Using the table below, please state in which aspects of your pilot would you like to involve external stakeholders that are not part of the consortium (e.g. to discuss new business models, feedback on the product features, market appetite for the services you are testing, to understand drivers and barriers to their adoption, etc.)

Stakeholder category	Briefly describe how you would like them to be involved

--	--

3. What other types of customers (other than the ones serviced in your pilot) would be serviced if taken to the market phase?
4. Any other stakeholders you would like to consider in the living lab activities?

9.4. Appendix D: Stakeholder consultation register

Purpose of the document

The stakeholder consultation process will incorporate many activities across a variety of contexts. Therefore, it is essential that each activity is properly monitored and recorded. The “consultation register” below shows the details that may be required to be documented to ensure smooth feedback loops are established between stakeholders and project partners and also for reporting purposes. After each stakeholder engagement activity, please send the GECO team the table below filled in with the relevant information.

Information required	Explanation of how to fill in the table
Partner	<i>SYNERGY project partner leading the engagement activity</i>
Relevant Work Package / Task / Deliverable	<i>Please link the stakeholder engagement activity to a specific Work Package / Task / Deliverable</i>
Engagement method	<i>Please describe the engagement method(s) e.g. Seminar / workshop / focus group / interview/ email / negotiation game (non-exhaustive list)</i>
Date	<i>Date the engagement activity took place</i>
Stakeholder group(s)	<i>Describe the type of audience which attended the event</i>
Points of contact	<i>Stakeholder name(s) and contact details AND/OR organisation(s)</i>
Size of audience	<i>How many people did you engage in this particular event</i>
Coverage	<i>Local / regional / national / European level / Other</i>
Purpose of the engagement	<i>Please describe as precisely as possible the purpose of the stakeholder engagement</i>